

Geospatial Modeling of Soil Properties Using Satellite Embeddings and Machine Learning

Andrej Slapničar¹, Marina Bagić Babac^{1,*}, Vedran Mornar²

¹ University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, Zagreb, Croatia, andrej.slapnicar@fer.hr, marina.bagic@fer.hr

² VERN' University, Zagreb, Croatia, vedran.mornar@vern.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Machine learning is increasingly used in environmental monitoring to fill the gaps between sparse field data and satellite observations. This study evaluates multiple machine learning models using satellite embedding features for predicting soil properties and land characteristics across large geographic areas. We combine georeferenced data from the LUCAS 2018 Soil Module with 64-dimensional embeddings from Google's Satellite Embedding Dataset (SED), which capture spectral and spatial characteristics of the Earth's surface. These embeddings are used as input to supervised machine learning models for predicting key soil properties, such as organic carbon and pH, and land cover classes. All models are validated using field measurements from the LUCAS dataset. The results demonstrate the ability of satellite-based feature extraction to be used for predicting soil properties that cannot be observed directly from space. By generalizing from point-based measurements to continuous maps, this approach enables high-resolution modeling of soil and environmental variables. The system is designed to be scalable, and future work will include more parameters, models, and continental coverage to support soil monitoring, carbon estimation, and environmental policy planning.

Keywords: satellite embeddings; machine learning; soil property prediction; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Machine learning has become an important tool in environmental monitoring, which enables efficient large-scale analyses. In soil science, traditional methods of assessing soil properties require laboratory analysis of collected samples, which is often costly and time-consuming. Digital soil mapping addresses this by combining field observations with spatial predictors to estimate soil attributes across landscapes (McBratney et al. 2003, Hengl et al. 2007).

Multispectral satellite imagery and derived indicators have been widely used as predictors of soil properties (Hengl et al. 2017), but these approaches typically rely on features such as spectral bands or vegetation indices, so their effectiveness depends on the ability of such features to capture relevant environmental signals.

Machine learning methods enable modeling nonlinear relationships between environmental variables and soil attributes (Wadoux et al. 2020). Algorithms such as random forest, gradient boosting, and neural networks have shown strong performance, but most existing studies rely on predefined variables rather than representations derived

from satellite data. Foundation models trained on Earth observation data change this by learning representations that can be expressed as satellite embeddings, compact vector features that encode spectral and spatial land surface information (Cong et al. 2022, Mendieta et al. 2023, Szwarcman et al. 2024). The Satellite Embedding Dataset (SED), derived from Google's AlphaEarth foundation model, provides such representations in the form of fixed-length embeddings for each location (Brown et al. 2025). Other satellite embedding resources have also recently been introduced, such as TESSERA, which provides global pixel-level temporal embeddings from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 time-series data (Feng et al. 2025). These embeddings can be used for a range of downstream tasks, including land cover classification and environmental analysis (Ryan et al. 2026), as well as regression of biophysical variables using field observations (Jin et al. 2026). This suggests that such embeddings may serve as features for geospatial modeling. However, their usefulness for soil property prediction, particularly for variables that are not directly observable from space, remains insufficiently explored.

This study addresses these challenges by evaluating SED embeddings as a satellite-derived feature representation for predicting soil properties and land characteristics from LUCAS 2018 observations. Multiple machine learning models are trained and compared under a consistent experimental setup using SED embeddings as a common input representation. Target variables include organic carbon, pH, nitrogen, phosphorus, electrical conductivity, land cover, and land use. The primary objective is to evaluate how different downstream machine learning models perform when using pretrained satellite embeddings as input features for soil property prediction and land classification tasks.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Dataset

The models were developed using a combination of field-based soil observations and satellite-derived features. Soil data were obtained from the LUCAS 2018 Soil Module, which provides harmonized, georeferenced soil measurements across Europe (Orgiazzi et al. 2018). Measured attributes include organic carbon, pH, nitrogen, phosphorus, electrical conductivity, land cover and land use. Descriptive statistics for the soil properties used in the regression tasks are provided in Table 1, and the class

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of soil properties used for regression.

Variable	n	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max	IQR
Electrical conductivity (EC)	18975	18.39	25.56	0.24	13.95	1295.60	12.51
Nitrogen (N)	18969	3.16	3.72	0.20	2.00	46.50	2.10
Organic carbon (OC)	18949	47.61	81.65	2.10	21.80	723.90	29.60
Phosphorus (P)	13981	34.72	27.55	0.30	26.50	515.00	27.40
pH(CaCl ₂)	18983	5.71	1.40	2.60	5.80	9.80	2.60
pH(H ₂ O)	18983	6.26	1.32	3.34	6.29	10.43	2.38

distributions for the land cover and land use classification tasks are shown in Table 2. After excluding rare classes, the classification tasks contained 18,979 samples across seven land cover classes and 18,924 samples across eleven land use classes. To represent environmental conditions at each sampling location, satellite-derived features were obtained from the Satellite Embedding Dataset (SED), available through Google Earth Engine (Google Earth Engine 2025, Brown et al. 2025). SED provides annual embedding fields from large-scale geospatial foundation models, where each location is represented by a fixed-length vector encoding multi-sensor spectral, spatial, and temporal information. The embeddings were spatially aligned with the geographic coordinates of the soil observations from

LUCAS. Records with missing values in either soil attributes or embedding features were removed prior to analysis.

2.2 Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing was performed to integrate soil observations from the LUCAS dataset with satellite-derived embedding features. First, LUCAS soil samples were filtered to retain records with valid geographic coordinates and complete measurements for the selected target variables. SED embeddings were extracted at the corresponding coordinates, associating each sample with a 64-element feature vector. For classification tasks, classes below a minimum sample threshold were excluded to reduce class imbalance. The dataset was split into training and testing subsets using an 80:20 split, with

Table 2. Class distribution for land cover and land use classification tasks.

Variable	Class	n	Share (%)
Land cover (LC)	Cropland	7430	39.15
	Woodland	6092	32.10
	Grassland	3988	21.01
	Shrubland	720	3.79
	Bareland	638	3.36
	Artificial land	71	0.37
	Wetlands	40	0.21
	1 excluded rare class (Water)	5	0.03
Land use (LU)	Agriculture (excluding fallow land and kitchen gardens)	10931	57.76
	Forestry	5603	29.61
	Semi-natural and natural areas not in use	1284	6.79
	Fallow land	737	3.89
	Other abandoned areas	123	0.65
	Amenities, museum, leisure (e.g. parks, botanical gardens)	66	0.35
	Electricity, gas and thermal power distribution	56	0.30
	Residential	54	0.29
	Road transport	35	0.18
	Kitchen gardens	23	0.12
	Mining and quarrying	12	0.06
	15 excluded rare classes	60	0.32

stratified random sampling applied for classification tasks and random sampling applied for regression tasks.

2.3 Machine Learning Methods

A range of machine learning models was used to evaluate the predictive performance of satellite embeddings for soil property estimation. The selected models include Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM as tree-based ensemble methods, and a multilayer perceptron (MLP) as a neural network baseline. All models were trained using the same input features derived from satellite embeddings to ensure a consistent comparison across methods. Default or lightly tuned hyperparameters were used for initial experiments, while selected models were further optimized using randomized hyperparameter search. In addition, class imbalance was addressed using SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) in selected cases where it resulted in improved model performance (Chawla et al. 2002).

2.4 Evaluation Metrics

The performance of the models was evaluated separately for classification and regression tasks. For classification, overall accuracy was used as a general measure of performance, while balanced accuracy was included to account for class imbalance by averaging recall across classes. In addition, precision, recall, and F1-score were computed using macro and weighted averaging to provide complementary insights into performance across all classes. Cohen's kappa coefficient was also calculated as an additional metric, although its limitations have been noted in recent studies. For regression tasks, model performance was evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean squared error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE). In addition, the concordance correlation coefficient (CCC) was used to assess the agreement between predicted and observed values, and the ratio of performance to interquartile range (RPIQ) was included as a scale-independent metric commonly used in soil property prediction.

3 Results

A total of 32 models were developed using four machine learning algorithms, including Random Forest (RF), XGBoost (XGB), LightGBM (LGBM), and a multilayer

Table 3. Best-performing models for each soil property based on R^2 score.

Variable	Machine learning method	R^2	RMSE	MAE	RPIQ	CCC
Electrical conductivity (EC)	MLP	0.215	21.130	9.680	0.588	0.318
Nitrogen (N)	MLP	0.346	2.838	1.517	0.740	0.546
Organic carbon (OC)	MLP	0.387	65.472	29.544	0.461	0.579
Phosphorus (P)	MLP	0.138	26.608	16.920	1.034	0.251
pH(CaCl ₂)	MLP	0.719	0.740	0.576	3.515	0.836
pH(H ₂ O)	MLP	0.714	0.703	0.548	3.314	0.833

perceptron (MLP), across both classification and regression tasks. For each target variable, the best-performing model was selected based on the primary evaluation metric. For regression, six soil properties were evaluated using satellite embedding features. As shown in Table 3, the highest predictive accuracy was obtained for pH-related variables, where the MLP model achieved R^2 values of 0.719 for pH(CaCl₂) and 0.714 for pH(H₂O). Nitrogen and organic carbon were predicted with moderate accuracy, with best-performing models achieving R^2 values in the range of 0.35–0.40. In contrast, electrical conductivity and phosphorus showed lower predictive performance, with R^2 values below 0.25 for all models. Lower RMSE and MAE values were observed for pH variables, while higher errors were recorded for electrical conductivity and phosphorus. The RPIQ and CCC metrics also reflect these differences in performance, with pH variables having higher values and variables that are harder to predict having lower values. The R^2 scores of the best regression models for each machine learning method are presented in Table 4. Across all regression tasks, the highest R^2 scores were obtained with the MLP model, while tree-based models showed lower but comparable performance.

For classification, the best-performing models for land cover and land use are presented in Table 5. For land cover classification, the highest performance was achieved by

Table 4. R^2 scores of the best regression models for each ML method.

Variable	RF	XGB	LGBM	MLP
Electrical conductivity (EC)	0.161	0.160	0.159	0.215
Nitrogen (N)	0.331	0.337	0.336	0.346
Organic carbon (OC)	0.369	0.380	0.370	0.387
Phosphorus (P)	0.136	0.133	0.132	0.138
pH(CaCl ₂)	0.691	0.714	0.712	0.719
pH(H ₂ O)	0.688	0.707	0.711	0.714

Table 5. Best-performing models for land cover and land use classification based on macro F1-score.

Variable	Machine learning method	F1 (macro)	Precision (macro)	Recall (macro)	OA	BA	κ
		F1 (weighted)	Precision (weighted)	Recall (weighted)			
Land cover (LC)	MLP	0.569	0.682	0.522	0.829	0.522	0.750
		0.820	0.820	0.829			
Land use (LU)	MLP	0.282	0.291	0.277	0.828	0.277	0.698
		0.824	0.821	0.828			

Table 6. Macro F1-scores of the best classification models for each ML method.

Variable	RF	XGB	LGBM	MLP
Land cover (LC)	0.530	0.480	0.535	0.569
Land use (LU)	0.254	0.260	0.267	0.282

the MLP model, with an overall accuracy of 0.829 and a macro-averaged F1-score of 0.569. For land use classification, the best results were also obtained using the MLP model, with an overall accuracy of 0.828 and a macro-averaged F1-score of 0.282. Macro-averaged metrics were substantially lower than weighted metrics, particularly for land use classification. The macro F1-scores of the best classification models for each machine learning method are presented in Table 6. The highest macro F1-score for both land cover and land use classification was achieved by the MLP model, while the differences among tree-based models were smaller.

4 Discussion

Predictive performance varied considerably across soil properties. The highest predictive performance was achieved for pH-related variables, which is consistent with their indirect links to vegetation patterns and land management that are well captured by satellite observations (Hengl et al. 2017, Wadoux et al. 2020). Nitrogen and organic carbon showed moderate performance, as they are influenced by surface processes such as vegetation dynamics, but also by subsurface composition and management history that embeddings do not fully capture. Electrical conductivity and phosphorus performed worst, as both depend on localized soil chemistry and subsurface processes, which are not effectively represented in satellite-derived features.

For classification tasks, models achieved relatively high overall accuracy, while macro-averaged metrics were substantially lower, particularly for land use classification. This indicates that dominant classes were predicted reliably, whereas minority classes were not. The discrepancy between macro and weighted metrics reflects the strong class imbalance shown in Table 2, where minority classes have very limited representation and are therefore difficult for the models to learn. For this reason, macro-averaged scores provide a more informative assessment in this context.

One limitation of this study is that the models rely exclusively on satellite embedding features without

incorporating additional environmental variables like climate data and topography, which are commonly used in digital soil mapping. The absence of these variables may limit the ability of the models to capture properties that are not directly observable from satellite imagery. In addition, the LUCAS dataset represents soil conditions in Europe, which may affect the ability to generalize models to other geographic regions and environmental conditions.

Future work should explore the integration of satellite embeddings with additional environmental predictors to improve model performance, particularly for properties that are hard to observe from surface observations. In addition, future studies should compare SED-based models with models trained directly on conventional EO predictors, such as Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data and derived indices, to better assess the added value of satellite embeddings relative to traditional remote-sensing features. Further investigation of embedding representations, including comparison with other satellite embedding products such as TESSERA, as well as different model architectures and combining temporal information, may also enhance predictive capability. Expanding the analysis to larger and more diverse datasets, and evaluating alternative machine learning methods, could further improve the model robustness and performance.

5 Conclusions

This study demonstrates that satellite embedding features combined with machine learning methods can be used for predicting soil properties and land characteristics at large spatial scales. The results show that predictive performance varies considerably across target variables. High accuracy was achieved for pH properties, while moderate performance was obtained for nitrogen and organic carbon, and electrical conductivity and phosphorus showed substantially lower predictive performance. For classification tasks, models achieved high overall accuracy. However, macro-averaged metrics revealed reduced performance, particularly for land use classification. The findings indicate that satellite embeddings work well for soil properties tied to surface

conditions, but less so for those driven by subsurface processes and localized variability. Although this method has limitations, it represents a practical approach for linking satellite features to field observations. Future work should combine satellite embeddings with climate and topographic covariates to improve performance for subsurface properties. Also, further research on embedding representations and model architectures could improve the ability to better capture complex relationships between soil and environmental variables.

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